

How can crop science cultivate more “Strong Female Leads”

Alison Bentley and Nele Verhulst

A Women in Crop Science book review of ‘Strong Female Lead’ by Arwa Mahdawi

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Organizations around the world are changing. Amongst the evolution is a reflection (and/or desire for action and correction) of the importance of diversity and inclusion in organizations. Many authors have documented the importance of not only human diversity but also cognitive diversity (e.g. a favorite book on this topic is ‘Rebel Ideas’ by Matthew Syed). However, despite clear evidence for the importance of diversity as a driver of innovative thinking and highly functioning, responsive organizations, one of the traps of many institutions is a proverbial “box-ticking” and/or the fostering of human, but not cognitive diversity.

In her book ‘Strong Female Lead: Lessons from Women in Power’, Arwa Mahdawi describes significant gaps in current models of leadership, and highlights important differences between male and female “coded” leadership traits. Rather than pushing females to “lean in” (see ‘Lean In: Women, Work, and the Will to Lead’ by Nell Scovell and Sheryl Sandberg) to traditionally male coded leadership traits, she makes the case for “leaning out” and embracing female coded traits that challenge the traditional archetypes of leaders.

Many agricultural and crop science research organizations have been historically dominated by male leaders and male coded management approaches. Times are changing: and in our spheres of work we see increasing female representation (e.g. <https://archive.wheat.org/five-in-five-blog-series-5-re-evaluating-metrics-of-success-and-adopting-new-ways-of-working/>). What more can be done? How do we cultivate and grow strong female leads in crop science?

Review our expectations of current leaders

Firstly, we need to recognize and review the characteristics we expect (and reward) in our current leaders. Rather than defining success through KPIs and metrics reflecting dominance, individual success, and visibility, we need to create reward structures that acknowledge female-coded traits.

Create safe spaces to accommodate divergent views

As Arwa Mahdawi remarks “confidence doesn’t equal competence” and loud voices should no longer continue to dominate organizational viewpoints. The agile, responsive organizations of the future will need to seek input from across their talent base. Forget reporting lines and personal power, open space (physical and metaphorical) to allow and

reward collaboration and new ideas to develop and grow. This will also build a foundation of future leaders who aren't afraid to call out hypocrisy and stand up for their values.

Re-define future leadership

Leadership that embraces female coded traits offers huge potential to organizations. Arwa Mahdawi discusses the pitfalls of traditional empowerment (e.g. senior figures giving out power and insisting this creates people who are empowered) and argues instead for a holistic relinquishing of top-down control in order to achieve leadership beyond self-interest.

Remember, you “don't need a rocket”

Research environments tend to emphasize and reward 'cutting edge' ideas and technology (the book discusses the example of building rockets to Mars for when the planet becomes inhabitable, rather than reducing greenhouse gas emissions on the Earth we inhabit today). Alternatively, we should prioritize research and innovation guided by impact, inclusivity, and pragmatism, which tend to be more female coded traits. As Arwa Mahdawi summarizes in a sentence that seems especially relevant for crop scientists “It's possible to think big while keeping your feet rooted firmly on the ground”.

Women don't just bring an optic of diversity to organizations like ours. They bring unique and powerful strengths. Many of our institutional structures and reward structures were built by and for male coded leadership. It's time not just to focus on achieving diversity *per se*, but on building new organizations that make the most of the available portfolio of traits in the workforce.

Learn more & read the book here: <https://linktr.ee/ARWAMAHDAWI>